

EFFECT OF DIFFERENT TYPES OF MULCHES ON YIELD AND QUALITY ATTRIBUTES OF CUSTARD APPLE Cv.Dharur -6

* Dr.G.R. Munde, **Dr R.V.Nainwad and ***Dr.V.S.Shinde

* Officer In-charge, Custard Apple Research Station, Ambajogai

**Asstt. Professor, Fruit Research Station, Aurangabad

*** Asstt Professor ,College of Agriculture. Latur , Maharashtra, India.

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Abstract

The present investigation entitled "Different types of mulches on off season bearing of custard apple (*Annona squamosa* L.) cv. Dharur 6" was conducted on well-established custard apple orchard of six year old at Custard Apple Research Station, Ambajogai, during 2022-23. The experiment was conducted to study different types of mulches on off season bearing of custard apple (*Annona squamosa* L.) cv. Dharur 6. The experiment was carried out in Randomized block design with seven treatments replicated thrice. The treatment were as (T1) wheat straw, (T2) Dried grass, (T3) soyabean straw, (T4) sugarcane bagasse, (T5) Dhaincha, (T6) Black coated plastic sheet and (T7) Control. The yield per plant (14.63 kg) and yield per ha (8.76 q) was recorded in treatment T6 (Black coated plastic paper). As regards to chemical attributes like Total Soluble Solids (24.53%), Total Sugar (20.16%), Reducing Sugar (17.61%) and Non-reducing Sugar (2.12%) was recorded in treatment T6 (Black coated plastic paper).

Keywords: Custard Apple, mulching, Mulches, quality and yield).

Introduction

Custard apple (*Annona squamosa*) is a member of family annonaceae, having chromosome number is $2n=14$. It is one of the delicious fruit due to present of pleasant flavour, mild aroma and sweet test have a universal acceptance. Custard apple is also known by different name such as sweet soap, Sitaphal, sharifa, and 'attichaka' in various growing regions. In india mainly grown in Bihar, Madhya Pradesh, Assam, Maharashtra, Odisha, Rajasthan, Andhra Pradesh and Tamilnadu. In Maharashtra it is commonly grown in Solapur, Aurangabad, Beed, Pune, Buldhana, Dhule, Nagpur, Aurangabad and Akola Districts. In Marathwada region it is mainly grown in Beed, Ambajogai, Latur, Daulatabad and Aurangabad. Custard apple is grown in tropical climate, having semi deciduous in nature. Flowers are greenish yellow in colour have six petals and two whorls, numerous stamens and carpel.

It requires high humidity which is necessary during flowering to improve fruit set. It requires 60-80cm annual rainfall for better growth and development. It requires summer temperature from 15 to 25^o C. It can not stand frost and or a cold for long period. Soil should be sandy loam having pH neutral to slightly acidic. Hand

pollination is practiced in custard apple to enhance the fruit set. Due to high temperature, low atmospheric humidity, lack of irrigation water and natural stresses results in less number of flowers, poor fruit setting and low yield and degraded quality of fruit too (pande and kamboj 2005). The nutritive value of custard apple is very high. It contains Magnesium, which helps in protecting heart against diseases as well as relaxing muscles. It has many alkaloids, such as nicocodine, sqamorine, aporphine, romerine, squamonine, corydine, norisocorriyidine, glaucine and anononaine in different parts of the plants. Custard apple seeds has insecticidal and abortifacient properties.

Materials and Method

The present study "Different types of mulches on off season bearing of Custard Apple (*Annona squamosa* L.)" was conducted during the year 2022-23. The details of the materials used, method adopted and statistical analysis followed during the course of this investigations are described below. The experiment was carried out at instructional-cum-research field of Custard apple Research Station, Ambajogai, Vasantrao Naik Marathwada Krishi Vidhyapeeth Parbhani, during the year 2022-23.

Details of the Experiment

1	Name of the crop	Custard apple (<i>Annona squamosa</i> L.)
2	Family	Annonaceae
3	Variety	Dharur-6
4	Experimental Design	Randomized Block Design
5	Number of treatments	7
6	Spacing	5 × 5 m
7	Number of replications	Three (03)
8	Number plant / treatment	Three (03)
9	Total Number of plant	63
10	Number of mulches	Six (06)

Details of the treatment:

Treatment No.	Treatment details	Thickness (cm)
T1	Wheat straw	5-7cm
T2	Dried grass	5-7cm
T3	Soybean straw	5-7cm
T4	Sugarcane bagasse	5-7 cm
T5	Dhaincha	5-7 cm
T6	Black coated plastic sheet	(100 μ)
T7	Control (without mulch)	-

The experiment was carried out on well-established Custard apple Cv. (Dharur6) orchard with the tree spacing of 5×5 m at Custard apple Research station, Ambajogai during 2022-23. The experiment consists of 07 treatment with 3 replications in Randomized Block Design (RBD). with 3 plant per treatment. Mulching materials was laid out in the field with 3 plant per treatment in summer season. The

statistical analysis was completed by standard statistical method suggested by Panse and Sukhatme (1995).

Result and Discussion

The field experiment entitled "Studies on Different types of mulches on off season bearing of custard apple (*Annona squamosa* L.)" was carried out at instructional-cum-research field of Custard

apple Research Station, Ambajogai, Vasantrao Naik Marathwada Krishi Vidyapeeth, Parbhani during the year 2022-23. The data has been statistically analyzed by using randomized block design. The results obtained are presented under suitable headings.

Effect of types of mulches on yield per plant (kg)

Significant variation was observed among all the treatments for yield per plant (Table 1). The yield per plant ranged from 10.09 to 14.63 kg. Maximum yield per plant was recorded in treatment black coated plastic sheet (T6, 14.63 kg) followed by treatments Dried grass (T2, 12.20 kg) and Wheat straw (T1, 11.58 kg). Minimum yield per plant was recorded in treatment Soybean straw (T7, 10.07

Table 1 Effect of types of mulches on yield per plant (kg)

Treatment	Treatment details	Yield per plant(kg)
T1	Wheat straw	11.58
T2	Drying grass	12.20
T3	Soybean straw	10.07
T4	Sugarcane baggase	11.60
T5	Dhaincha	11.56
T6	Black coated plastic paper	14.63
T7	Control	10.09
	S. E. ±	0.21
	C. D. at 5%	0.67

Yield per ha (t)

Significant variation was observed among all the treatments for yield per ha (Table 2). Yield per ha ranged from 6.90 to 8.76 t/ha. Maximum yield per ha was recorded in treatment Black coated plastic sheet (T6, 8.76 t/ha) which was statistically at par with the Soybean straw (T2, 8.30 t/ha) and Sugarcane baggase (T4, 8.20 t/ha). Minimum yield per ha was recorded in treatment Control (T7, 6.90 t/ha).

Black polythene mulch increased fruit yield of Pomegranate then control (Ghosh and Bera, 2015). Effect of the different mulches on

Table 2 Effect of types of mulches on Yield per ha (t)

Treatment	Treatment details	Yield per ha (t)
T1	Wheat straw	7.19
T2	Dried grass	7.77
T3	Soybean straw	8.30
T4	Sugarcane baggase	8.20
T5	Dhaincha	8.16
T6	Black coated plastic sheet	8.76
T7	Control	6.90
	S. E. ±	0.45
	C. D. at 5%	1.41

Quality parameters

Total Soluble Solids (%)

Significant variation was observed among all the treatments for total soluble solids (Table 3). Total soluble solid ranged from 19.09 to 24.53 %. Maximum total soluble solids were recorded in treatment Black coated plastic sheet (T6, 24.53 %) followed by treatments Dhaincha (T5, 24.30 %) and Soybean straw (T3, 23.76 %). which were at par. and Minimum total soluble solids was recorded in treatment control (T7, 19.09 %).

The most desirable changes in chemical quality parameter like

Table 3 Effect of types of mulches on Total Soluble Solids (TSS %)

Treatment	Treatment details	TSS (%)
T1	Wheat straw	22.43
T2	Dried grass	20.53
T3	Soybean straw	23.76
T4	Sugarcane baggase	23.46
T5	Dhaincha	24.30
T6	Black coated plastic sheet	24.53
T7	Control	19.09

kg).

Highest fruit yield of ber under the black polythene mulch treatment and least yield was in control (Bal and Singh, 2011). Impact of different mulching materials on growth, yield and quality of strawberry reported significantly higher fruit yield under the transparent and black polythene mulch and minimum in control (Kumar and Dey 2011). They also explained that increase fruit yield in the plants under black polyethylene mulch as compared to unmulched (control trees) may be due to better conservation of soil moisture and suppression of weed growth.

soil moisture conservation, weed reduction, growth and yield under the black polythene mulch and followed by grass mulch (Shirgure *et al.* 2003).

Highest fruit yield of Ber under the black polythene mulch treatment and least yield was in control (Bal and Singh, 2011). Impact of different mulching materials on growth, yield and quality of strawberry reported significantly higher fruit yield under the transparent and black polythene mulch and minimum in control (Kumar and Dey 2011).

reducing, non-reducing sugar, ascorbic acid, acidity content might be due to the proper availability of soil moisture content continuously during the experiment period and improved nutrient status while controlling the fluctuation in temperature and lower soil moisture contents with the severe weed infestation was the main cause of low-quality fruit. Above findings were agreement with below. Under the different organic and inorganic mulching materials and reported under the highest vitamin-C content of fruit pulp with black polythene mulch (Bakshi *et al.* 2014).

S. E. ±	0.43
C. D. at 5%	1.32

Total sugars (%)

Significant variation was observed among all the treatments for total sugar (Table 4). Total sugar ranges from 18.54 to 20.16 %. Maximum total sugar was recorded in treatment Black coated plastic sheet (T₆, 20.16 %) followed by treatments Dried grass (T₂, 19.94 %) and Wheat straw (T₅, 19.63 %). which were at par. and Minimum total sugar was recorded in Soybean straw (T₇, 18.54 %). Higher total soluble solids, acidity content of lime fruits with black polythenemulch and grass mulch in acid lime (*Citrus aurantifolia*

Swingle L) Shirgure (2012).The maximum total sugar under the black polythene mulch and minimum was in control treatment in strawberry cv. Chandler (Bakshi *et al.* 2014).

The use of black polythene mulch with black side facing led to improvement in total sugar, reducing sugar, non-reducing sugar and also significantly shows the rind thickness (Lalruatsangi and Hazarika 2018). Similarly in satsuma mandarin with increased total sugar, reducing sugar and ascorbic acid content was observed in trees mulched with black

Table 4. Effect of types of mulches on Total sugars (%)

Treatment	Treatment details	Total sugar (%)
T ₁	Wheat straw	19.63
T ₂	Dried grass	19.94
T ₃	Soybean straw	18.54
T ₄	Sugarcane baggase	19.46
T ₅	Dhaincha	19.36
T ₆	Black coated plastic sheet	20.16
T ₇	Control	19.22
	S. E. ±	0.48
	C. D. at 5%	1.50

Reducing sugars (%)

Significant variation was observed among all the treatments for reducing sugar (Table 5). Reducing sugar ranged from 17.51 to 17.99 %. Maximum reducing sugar per cent was recorded in treatment dried grass (T₂, 17.99 %) which were at par. and followed by treatments dhaincha (T₅, 17.98 %) and soybean (T₃, 17.91 %). Minimum reducing sugar per cent was recorded in treatment wheat straw (T₁, 17.51 %).

Swingle L) Shirgure (2012).The maximum total sugar under the black polythene mulch and minimum was in control treatment in strawberry cv. Chandler (Bakshi *et al.* 2014).

The use of black polythene mulch with black side facing led to improvement in total sugar, reducing sugar, non-reducing sugar and also significantly shows the rind thickness (Lalruatsangi and Hazarika 2018). Similarly in satsuma mandarin with increased total sugar, reducing sugar and ascorbic acid content was observed in trees mulched with black.

Higher total soluble solids, acidity content of lime fruits with black polythenemulch and grass mulch in acid lime (*Citrus aurantifolia*

Table 5. Effect of types of mulches on Reducing sugars (%)

Treatment	Treatment details	Reducing sugar (%)
T ₁	Wheat straw	17.51
T ₂	Dried grass	17.99
T ₃	Soybean straw	17.91
T ₄	Sugarcane baggase	17.73
T ₅	Dhaincha	17.98
T ₆	Black coated plastic sheet	17.61
T ₇	Control	17.93
	S. E. ±	0.17
	C. D. at 5%	0.54

Non-reducing sugars (%)

Significant variation was observed among all the treatments for non-reducing sugar (Table 4.16). Non-reducing sugar ranged from 2.01 to 2.12 %. Maximum non-reducing sugar was recorded in treatment black coated plastic sheet (T₆, 2.12 %) followed by treatments Wheat straw (T₁, 2.11 %) and Minimum non-reducing sugar per cent was recorded in treatments Sugarcane baggase (T₄, 2.01 %). The use of black polythene mulch with black side facing led to improvement in total sugar, reducing sugar, non-reducing sugar and

also significantly shows the rind thickness (Lalruatsangi and Hazarika 2018). Similarly in satsuma mandarin with increased total sugar, reducing sugar and ascorbic acid content was observed in trees mulched with black.

Higher total soluble solids, acidity content of lime fruits with black polythenemulch and grass mulch in acid lime (*Citrus aurantifolia* Swingle L) Shirgure (2012).The maximum total sugar under the black polythene mulch and minimum was in control treatment in strawberry cv. Chandler (Bakshi *et al.* 2014).

Table 6 Effect of types of mulches on Non-reducing sugars (%)

Treatment	Treatment details	Non-reducing sugar (%)
T ₁	Wheat straw	2.11
T ₂	Dried grass	2.06
T ₃	Soybean straw	2.04
T ₄	Sugarcane baggase	2.01
T ₅	Dhaincha	2.06
T ₆	Black coated plastic sheet	2.12

T7	Control	2.07
	S. E. \pm	0.03
	C. D. at 5%	0.11

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